

Q2 - How long have you been working in this organization?

Q3 - How long have you been working in the field of information sciences in general?

Q5 - Do you currently undertake any digital preservation activities or have a defined workflow for dealing with the preservation of digital information?

Q6 - How would you describe the current state of your organization's digital preservation practices?

Q7 - Does your organization have a formal email archiving policy or strategic framework? (This may include a written policy, preservation plan, documented strategy, or formalized procedures.)

Q8 - What types of digital documents does your organization need to preserve long-term? (Select all that apply)

Q9 - What system(s) does your organization use for digital preservation? - Selected Choice

Q9_8_TEXT - Other (please specify) - Text

Other (please specify) - Text

Axiell Collections

The Library has no system for Digital Preservation. (ask the Archives)

Until we get a proper DP solution, we "park" the documents in a SharePoint library

Q10 - What tools are used in your digital preservation workflow? (Select all that apply) - Selected Choice

Q10_6_TEXT - Other (please specify) - Text

Other (please specify) - Text

ShareGate

Q11 - What file formats does your organization use for long-term digital preservation?

Q12 - What standards or certifications does your organization use for digital preservation? (Select all that apply) - Selected Choice

Q13 - What metadata standards does your organization apply for digital preservation? (Select all that apply)

Q14 - How does your organization ensure the integrity and authenticity of preserved digital records? (Select all that apply)

Q15 - How does your organization handle format obsolescence? (Select all that apply)

Q16 - How does your organization ensure redundancy and backup for digital preservation? (Select all that apply)

Q17 - What are the major challenges your organization faces in digital preservation?

What are the major challenges your organization faces in digital preservation?

Lack of budget and human resources; lack of senior management interest/support

We are currently working to develop and implement a digital preservation strategy, including the establishment of the required processes and infrastructure. The biggest challenge in this is aligning understandings, visions and priorities of multiple internal stakeholders (Archives, Library, Information Management, IT, cybersecurity, etc.).

We have not embarked on digital preservation initiatives yet.

The quantity ; appraisal/selection ; workflows.

Lack of awareness of digital preservation needs. The organization has a generally low level of information management maturity, which means there are higher priority activities that need to be addressed before approaching the issue of digital preservation.

There is not digital preservation at the organization.

We are a small(ish) organization with limited resources; this is all a bit new to us

We are at the very beginning of the journey.

As a Library (not depository library), Digital preservation is not an issue, since most of our materials are commercial.

Millions of diverse records with heterogeneous content in thousands of data bases.

Lack of resources: our priority is to get on top of the management of current business records before we tackle digital preservation. We do not have the resources in our team to manage both at once.

Also, anticipating a potential lack of management buy-in: as long-term preservation is expensive and the awareness amongst our senior/middle management regarding the topic is low/non-existent. It may be difficult to secure support to purchase the necessary tools and technical support.

Ongoing budget and project cuts, as well as a lack of prioritization from our IT department.

Q18 - How are archived emails managed? (Select all that apply)

Q19 - Where are archived emails stored? (Select all that apply)

Q20 - What tools or systems does your organization use across the email archiving process?

Q21 - What file formats are used in your organization for long-term email preservation? (Select all that apply)

Q22 - What metadata is preserved alongside archived emails? (Select all that apply)

Q23 - What are the major challenges your organization faces in email archiving?

What are the major challenges your organization faces in email archiving?

lack of budget and human resources; lack of senior management support/interest

We have a retention policy for emails and a general policy of filing emails in our organization's enterprise content management system. However, we have yet to define a preservation strategy for our digital records.

Data privacy concerns hindering ability to create formal policy

Currently, IT practices preserves all email, without a robust or specific concept of "archiving"

There is no email archiving at the organization.

Starting to do it, actually

We are at the very beginning of the journey.

no archived e-mails

Doubles and dead links to attachments.

Lack of resources in our team to tackle this topic amidst competing demands.

Lack of interest and support from the IT department, no authority to enforce archiving practices among staff, and the absence of adequate systems and tools to carry out this work effectively.

Q24 - What is the approximate size of your organization?

Q25 - How many people are in your team? (Please enter a number)

How many people are in your team? (Please enter a number)

1

30

2.5

9

Archives : 5

Digital Preservation (IT) : 4

5

7

2

2

12

4

5